

Oxidation of Aromatic Carboxylic Acid Hydrazides by Chloramine-T. A Kinetic Study

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Kinetic investigations of oxidation of salicylic acid hydrazide and *o*-chlorobenzoic acid hydrazide in presence of alkaline methanol by chloramine-T (CAT) have been carried out at 30°. The end-products of the oxidation are bishydrazides, *p*-toluenesulphonamide and nitrogen. The rates were determined at different temperatures and activation parameters were evaluated. Zero effect of added salt, *p*-toluenesulphonamide and pH of medium was observed. The mechanism in which chloramine-T reacts with hydrazide giving acyldi-imide as an intermediate in the slow and rate-determining step has been proposed.

BROMAMINE-T (BAT)¹, bromamine-B (BAB)², chloramine-T (CAT)³ and dichloramine-T (DCT)⁴ are well-known organic oxidising reagents and several reports have been appeared on the mechanism of their reactions. But very little information is available on the mechanism of oxidation of hydrazides by chloramine-T (CAT). This prompted us to undertake this investigation.

Experimental

Both the hydrazides were prepared by the reported method⁵ and purified by repeated crystallisation. Chloramine-T and all other chemicals were of analytical grade. Methanol (Sarabhai Merck) and double-distilled water was used throughout. The kinetic procedure employed was the same as reported earlier⁶. The kinetics was followed by estimating the remaining amount of chloramine-T (CAT) iodometrically at different time intervals. The reactions were followed upto 75% and duplicate kinetic runs showed the results to be reproducible within 3%.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: In all sets of experiments, those we have carried out varying ratios of CAT-hydrazide, it is observed that two moles of hydrazides consumed two moles of CAT.

In the end-product analysis⁷, *p*-toluenesulphonamide and bishydrazide were detected by paper chromatography and tlc methods. Nitrogen was tested by lime test⁸. The observed stoichiometry may be represented as

where R represents O.HO.C₆H₄ and O.Cl.C₆H₄ in salicylic acid hydrazide and *o*-chlorobenzoic acid hydrazide, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The first order dependence on CAT was established by effecting a manifold variation in the [CAT] at 30° (Table 1) when the [substrates] is in excess. Plots of log [CAT]₀/[CAT] vs time are linear supporting the first order dependence of rate on [CAT]. These reactions follow first order

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF [OXIDANT] [HYDRAZIDE] AND TEMPERATURE** ON REACTION RATE*
pH=8.88, Temp =30° (unless otherwise mentioned)

[CAT] × 10 ⁴ M	[Hydrazide] × 10 ³ M		<i>k</i> ₁ × 10 ⁴ min ⁻¹		<i>k</i> ₂ × 10 ⁴ min ⁻¹	
	SAH	<i>o</i> -OBAH	SAH	<i>o</i> -OBAH	SAH	<i>o</i> -OBAH
2.00	2.00	2.00	4.02		0.86	
4.00	2.00	2.00	3.93		0.85	
6.00	2.00	2.00	4.83		0.87	
8.00	2.00	2.00	4.30		0.85	
10.00	2.00	2.00	4.72		0.89	
12.00	2.00	2.00	4.83		0.87	
5.00	0.50	1.50	0.99		0.62	
5.00	1.00	2.00	2.22		0.87	
5.00	1.50	2.50	3.61		1.05	
5.00	2.00	3.00	4.46		1.31	
5.00	2.50	3.50	5.99		1.50	
5.00	3.00	4.50	7.64		1.82	
8.00	1.50	1.50	2.28 ^a		0.67 ^a	
8.00	1.50	1.50	3.01 ^b		1.00 ^b	
8.00	1.50	1.50	3.96 ^c		1.43 ^c	
8.00	1.50	1.50	5.27 ^d		2.08 ^d	
8.00	1.50	1.50	6.66 ^e		3.04 ^e	

*Salicylic acid hydrazide (SAH): $E_a=42.61 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $A=7.30 \times 10^8 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger=-176.9 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta H^\ddagger=40.92 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta G^\ddagger=96.12 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$. *o*-chlorobenzoic acid hydrazide (*o*-OBAH): $E_a=61.51 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $A=2.68 \times 10^8 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger=-127.2 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta H^\ddagger=58.91 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta G^\ddagger=98.74 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.

**Temp : ^a30°, ^b35°, ^c40°, ^d45°, ^e50°

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SOLVENT COMPOSITION, SALT AND pH ON REACTION RATE

Temp. = 30°, pH = 8.88 (unless otherwise specified), [CAT] = 8.00 × 10⁻⁴ M, [hydrazide] = 1.5 × 10⁻³ M, [salt] = NaCl × 10⁻³ M

Methanol-H ₂ O % (v/v)	[NaCl] × 10 ³ M	pH	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ min ⁻¹ SAH*	k ₂ × 10 ⁴ min ⁻¹ o-CBAH*	
30-70	Nil	8.88	2.62	0.82	
40-60	Nil	8.88	2.40	0.75	
50-50	Nil	8.88	2.29	0.67	
60-40	Nil	8.88	1.89	0.63	
70-30	Nil	8.88	1.27	0.54	
80-20	Nil	8.88	0.71	—	
	(SAH)	(o-CBAH)			
50-50	0.00	2.00	8.88	2.28	0.70
50-50	1.00	4.00	8.88	2.28	0.70
50-50	2.00	6.00	8.88	2.25	0.68
50-50	3.00	8.00	8.88	2.18	0.69
50-50	—	10.00	8.88	—	0.70
50-50	Nil	Nil	8.86	2.46	—
50-50	Nil	Nil	8.88	2.28	—
50-50	Nil	Nil	9.80	1.14	—
50-50	Nil	Nil	9.90	1.57	—
50-50	Nil	Nil	8.75	—	7.26
50-50	Nil	Nil	9.25	—	6.14
50-50	Nil	Nil	9.37	—	6.71
50-50	Nil	Nil	10.30	—	7.42
50-50	Nil	Nil	10.71	—	7.69
50-50	Nil	Nil	10.80	—	7.22

*SAH = Salicylic acid hydrazide; o-CBAH = o-chlorobenzoic acid hydrazide.

kinetics with respect to hydrazide. In case of hydrazide, the order is confirmed by calculating the *k* values using the respective equation and applying the Van't Hoff equation,

$$\text{Order } n = \frac{\log [-dC_0/dt]_1 - \log [-dC_0/dt]_2}{\log [C_0]_1 - \log [C_0]_2}$$

Effects of addition of salt (NaCl) and pH of the solution were investigated (Table 2). Zero effect of TSA on reaction rate suggests that the post-equilibrium step involves a process in which TSA is one of the reaction products (equilibrium 4). The rates were measured at different temperatures and the activation parameters computed from the Arrhenius plots (Table 1). The effect of solvent composition (methanol-H₂O) was studied and the results are recorded in Table 2. From this study it can be concluded that reaction rate depends upon the polarity of solvent composition. The reaction is also carried out in the solutions of different pH and found that it is independent on pH of the solution (Table 2). Blank experiments showed that methanol is not oxidised by CAT under the experimental conditions. On the basis of equilibria shown by Singh⁹ in case of BAT, the following equilibria are possible in case of CAT^{9,10},

where Ts is *p*-CH₃C₆H₄SO₂.

Therefore, oxidising species in chloramine-T solution are *p*-toluenesulphonamide, hypochlorite ion, molecular chlorine and *N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulphonamide itself. Experimentally it was observed that added *p*-toluenesulphonamide had no effect on the rate of this oxidation indicating that it is not a probable oxidising species. The addition of sodium chloride does not enhance the rate of the reaction, so that intermediate formation of molecular chlorine is ruled out. The hypochlorite ion may not be involved in the reaction, otherwise reaction would have immeasurably fast. The only choice left is to assume chloramine-T as the real and most predominant oxidising species in this case. In case of bromamine-T oxidation, it was observed that BAT is the oxidising species¹¹. An increase in the amount of methanol in the solution decreases the polarity of the solvent and favours the process producing uncharged molecules from ions¹². It is observed that *N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulphonamide and hydrazide in 1:1 ratio react with each other in slow and rate determining step. Based on the above statements and experimental findings following mechanism is suggested :

or probable detailed pathway can be presented as follows :

where R is O.HO.C₆H₄ and O.Cl.C₆H₄. As R-CON=NH and HN=NH are very unstable the reactions represented by equations (8) and (9) are very fast.

The following rate equation may be derived for the above mechanism in terms of consumption of [CAT]

$$\frac{-d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = k [\text{CAT}] [\text{hydrazide}] \quad (10)$$

This rate law (equation 10) shows first order dependence on [CAT] and [hydrazide].

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